

File name	Purification condition
Sam-1-20150130	20mM HEPES, 250mM NaCl, 1mM MgCl ₂ 0.5% deoxy big CHAP, 0.5% Triton and protease inhibitors
Sam-S1-20210325	20mM HEPES, 250mM NaCl, 1mM MgCl ₂ 0.5% deoxy big CHAP, 0.5% Triton and protease inhibitors
Sam-S2-20210325	20mM HEPES, 250mM NaCl, 1mM MgCl ₂ 0.5% deoxy big CHAP, 0.5% Triton and protease inhibitors
Sam-S3-20210325	20mM HEPES, 20mM NaCl, 50mM TriSodium Citrate, 1mM MgCl ₂ 0.5% deoxy big CHAP, 0.5% Triton and protease inhibitors
Sam-BRF2-5min-20151209	20mM HEPES, 20mM NaCl, 50mM TriSodium Citrate, 1mM MgCl ₂ 0.5% deoxy big CHAP, 0.5% Triton and protease inhibitors
Sam-4-20150130	20mM HEPES, 250mM TriSodium Citrate, 1mM MgCl ₂ , 0.5% Triton and protease inhibitors
Sam-3-20150130	20mM HEPES, 250mM NaCl, 1mM MgCl ₂ , 0.5% Triton and protease inhibitors
M67b_buf5	20mM HEPES, 250mM NaCl, 1mM MgCl ₂ 0.5% deoxy big CHAP, 0.5% Triton and protease inhibitors